

NEW RIGHTS IN PREMIS

Enhanced options to manage RIGHTS metadata

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Abstract – This poster from the PREMIS Editorial Committee will update our community about the new version of the PREMIS data model. We aim to highlight the advantages of the updated version in documenting rights that are in place to allow all sorts of actions in our repositories

Submission Type – Poster.

Keywords – Metadata, Legal Rights, Legal License, Management, Standards

Conference Topics – Tūtaki – Encounter

I. INTRODUCTION

PREMIS (PREservation Metadata: Implementation Strategies) is a de facto international standard for describing Preservation Metadata, i.e. the information that a repository uses to support the digital preservation process. It is the result of international collaboration between many organizations and institutions since its inception, with representation from digital preservation practitioners and from producers and vendors of digital preservation systems.

It is formally defined by the PREMIS Data Dictionary[1]. The four basic elements of the PREMIS data model are: Objects (that we preserve), Events (which happen to these objects), Rights (which allow us to act) and Agents (that play an active or passive role in either Events or Rights).

The new version of the PREMIS data model will broaden the opportunities for the Rights element. This poster will demonstrate these opportunities and explain how the use of the Rights element can

strengthen documentation and provide support for digital preservation in practice.

II. Description of The Poster

The poster will consist of a diagrammatic representation of the revised data model, with brief explanations of the relationships and attributes that are introduced in the new version. It will present one new use for the model, several use cases have been analyzed as models for the final improvements.

III. Intended Audience

The new version of the PREMIS Data Dictionary will be published before the iPres Conference in Wellington. People may have heard about the new version, but not many will know the details. This poster is targeting all digital preservation practitioners interested in rights as part of preservation metadata. It can be practitioners that already know PREMIS who are keen to be updated about the new version and will want to explore the benefits of the new version, putting the Rights in place. The more general audience includes anyone interested in data modelling; they can get inspiration about how to represent and implement Rights in a digital archive.

1. REFERENCES

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